

Towards a seamless geospatial representation of freshwater habitats

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Abstract

Freshwater geospatial data processing is challenged by the structure of the dendritic stream network, where the longitudinal connectivity across the network needs to be addressed in complex workflows. In addition, standing water bodies such as lakes, ponds and reservoirs and their connectivity play a crucial role in structuring freshwater habitats. Yet, geospatial river and lake data is often not compatible given that the data stems from different sources, and remains spatially unconnected. In this report, we outline the single steps we used to integrate lakes into the Hydrography90m dataset and provide a set of tools and functions for identifying (i) lakes that intersect with the network, (ii) lake-network intersections, and (iii) upstream contributing areas to the single intersections. These functionalities are available in the *hydrographr* R-package (<https://github.com/flowabio/hydrographr>) as well as in the GeoFRESH online platform (<https://geofresh.org>), such that the Hydrography90m stream network now features direct linkages to the HydroLAKES dataset. The functions also enable the compatibility with the NASA SWOT water bodies at higher spatial resolution, such that custom water body data can be integrated into the Hydrography90m stream network. The pilot project provides an important step towards a seamless integration of freshwater water bodies such that rivers and lakes can be simultaneously addressed by the research communities within a single analysis workflow. Next steps include further streamlining the processing workflows regarding lakes within *hydrographr* and GeoFRESH.

I. Introduction

The objective of the 1-year pilot was to provide a seamless freshwater continuum across rivers and lakes at high spatial resolution. Geospatial datasets regarding stream and lakes have a different processing background: on the one hand, a stream network is typically delineated using a Digital Elevation Model (DEM), whereas on the other hand, lakes are digitized from remotely sensed measurements. Whereas geospatial stream datasets include the longitudinal connectivity intrinsically, lakes are typically stand-alone polygons without any network routing. To overcome this challenge, we developed scripting routines to integrate lakes into the Hydrography90m stream network dataset¹. The scripts were applied on the global HydroLAKES dataset² and tested likewise on the NASA SWOT data³.

The data processing challenge consisted in (i) harmonising and aligning the stream network and lake datasets by (ii) developing rules to address the longitudinal routing, followed by (iii) the amount of data and computing resources to achieve the integration of the Hydrography90m and HydroLAKES datasets at a global scale. We addressed these challenges by applying language integration given open-source geospatial processing tools, namely GidocsToolbox Workbench, GRASS GIS and GDAL/OGR. Moreover, we developed new functions for the *hydrographr* R-package⁴ to allow researchers to easily integrate the HydroLAKES (and other lake datasets) into the Hydrography90m stream network. Finally, we created a vignette to demonstrate possible workflows for freshwater research communities.

II. Results

The results of our pilot consist of (i) the global lake catchment database which (ii) is integrated into the GeoFRESH online platform; (iii) the development of lake functions for the *hydrographr* R package and (iv) a tutorial/vignette with an exemplary workflow for the R functions using the harmonized freshwater fish occurrence and abundance data set for 12 federal states in Germany⁵.

Global Lake Catchment database

We created a global lake catchment database, consisting of geo-spatial lake catchment information of 1.4 million lakes across the globe as provided in the HydroLAKES dataset². The database contains for each lake the lake catchment and lake surface in the GeoTIFF format, the lake outlet in the geodatabase format (Fig. 1) and in table format all intersection points between the Hydrography90m stream network and the lakes border (Tab. 1).

Figure 1 Global lake catchment database on the example of Lake Luzern (Switzerland); pink dot represents the lake outlet; black area shows the lake catchment of the outlet and the blue area the lake surface area.

Table 1 Intersection table on the example of the first four intersection points of Lake Luzern (Switzerland).

Outlet ID	HydroLAKE ID	Longitude	Latitude	Hydrography 90m Sub-catchment ID	Flow accumulation at pixel	Max Flow Accumulation 3 x 3 window	Mean Flow Accumulation 3 x 3 window
1	1248	8.3062	47.0512	8241857	2255.863	2256.822	752.218
2	1248	8.6079	46.8879	8209882	764.017	786.948	319.481
3	1248	8.6070	46.8879	8217888	702.034	771.058	317.751
4	1248	8.3070	47.0504	8064792	0.103	2255.863	250.679

The GeoFRESH online platform

As a first step, parts of the data of the global lake catchment database are integrated into the interactive, point and click GeoFRESH online platform (<https://geofresh.org/>). GeoFRESH is a PostgreSQL⁶/PostGIS⁷ database hosted at IGB. This includes the identification of HydroLAKES IDs at point occurrences (Fig. 2) and for those IDs the display of the lake outlet information in a new lake panel at the analysis section of the GeoFRESH platform (Fig. 3).

Upload and snap

Please provide your point data as a .csv table with three columns: a unique 'id', 'latitude', 'longitude'.

Coordinates should be provided in the WGS84 coordinate reference system. Column names are flexible. The number of points in your .csv file is currently limited to 1000, and upload file size should not exceed 1MB.

Point data (.csv format)

Browse... coord3.csv

Upload complete

Load test data

Snapping method: sub-catchment (default)

Points will be snapped to the nearest location on the river segment of the sub-catchment the point falls in.

Snap points

0%

Show 10 entries

Search:

ID	latitude	longitude	latitude_snap	longitude_snap	sub-catchment_ID	HydroLAKES_ID
1	47.63753	13.77857	47.64125	13.777083	91462884	168777
2	47.6463490576054	13.9350831959804	47.646549	13.934883	91458336	1349345
3	47.6481902947681	13.9281127981503	47.64819	13.927083	91451110	
4	47.6331973635864	13.897469351086	47.632917	13.897469	91469259	168795

Showing 1 to 5 of 5 entries

Download

Figure 2 GeoFRESH interface showing on top the snapped points in the *Upload and snap* panel in table format with the HydroLAKES ID for the points overlying with the corresponding HydroLAKES shapefile. On the bottom, the *Map* panel of the snapped points' location is shown.

In the next step, the user can visualize and download information about the lake outlet for each of the lakes that the uploaded and snapped points fall into (Fig. 3). The information includes point ID; lake ID; name of the lake (if known; retrieved from the HydroLAKES database); lake area (retrieved from the HydroLAKES database); Hydrography90m sub-catchment ID (named Outlet sub_c_id) and longitude and latitude of the outlet point coordinate.

LakeFRESH

UNDER development: the lake info module will be added soon!

Show entries Search:

ID	HydroLAKES ID	HydroLAKES name	HydroLAKES area (km ²)	Outlet subc_id	Outlet latitude	Outlet longitude
1	168777		1.83	5827375	47.6345833333333	13.7679166666667
2	1349345		0.34	5781039	47.64125	13.91875
4	168795		3.37	5858261	47.6220833333333	13.8279166666667
5	168795		3.37	5858261	47.6220833333333	13.8279166666667

Showing 1 to 4 of 4 entries Previous Next

Figure 3 GeoFRESH lake analysis panel presenting for each snapped occurrence point the lake outlet information of the respective lake

hydrographr lake functions

To increase the interoperability and customizability of the river and lake data integration, we developed three new R functions available in the *hydrographr* R-package. For a detailed workflow and in depth information on the presented functions, we refer to the lake tutorial vignette (available at https://glowabio.github.io/hydrographr/articles/case_study_lakes.html) and the *hydrographr* R-package (<https://github.com/glowabio/hydrographr>).

The new *hydrographr* R functions are:

1. *extract_lake_ids()*
2. *get_lake_intersection()*
3. *get_lake_catchment()*

The first function *extract_lake_ids()* gives users three different options to extract the HydroLAKE IDs of interest. Users can either set a bounding box and return all lake IDs within the bounding box; use the minimum and maximum extent of the coordinates found in the provided input user table or extract each lake ID for points from the user input table that spatially overlay with HydroLAKES polygons. The required input data for the function are a data frame or data table containing coordinates (longitude and latitude), i.e. of species occurrences and the HydroLAKES geo-spatial information either stored in shapefile or geodatabase format. Note that also other geo-spatial lake data can be used with this function as an input source. The output of the function is a data table containing the information of the input data, enriched with the lake ID of the given lake that overlaps with the point locations, or the IDs of those lakes that intersect with the bounding box.

The second function *get_lake_intersection()* returns a data table which contains information of all intersection points found between the Hydrography90m stream network and the geo-spatial lake polygons. The function uses the opensource morphological spatial pattern analysis (MSPA) tool from the GuidosToolbox Workbench (GWB)⁸ which needs to be first downloaded and installed by the user alongside with necessary data about the Hydrography90m stream network, flow accumulation and computational units. The output table with the lake IDs created in the *extract_lake_ids()* is then used as

an input to generate for each lake ID the intersection table called `coord_lake_{ID}.txt`, containing for all intersection points between the stream network and lake polygon (i.e. Hydrography90m and HydroLAKES lake polygons), the intersection ID, the lake ID, the coordinates of the intersection points (longitude and latitude values), the Hydrography90m sub-catchment ID, the flow accumulation value at the intersection point, the maximum and mean flow accumulation value (calculated by a 3 x 3 window around the intersection point), and the mean flow accumulation value. It also creates a raster GeoTIFF file of the lake surface and table with the lake extent called `lake_ref_{lakeID}.txt` both of which are needed for the third function `get_lake_catchment()`.

With the third function `get_lake_catchment()` users are able to delineate the lake catchment area from the intersection points, calculated in the previous function `get_lake_intersection()`. The user can choose the number of intersection points per lake and by this either receive only the entire lake catchment from the lake outlet (intersection point with the highest flow accumulation value) or delineate all sub-catchments of a lake using all intersection points as an input variable. The output lake catchments are stored in GeoTIFF format. Moreover, the function returns all intersection points of a lake used to delineate the lake catchments in geodatabase format.

Lake workflow vignette

To showcase the new R functions, we created a workflow example in a tutorial/vignette running an exemplary lake analysis with the data of the harmonized freshwater fish occurrence and the respective abundance data set. The vignette covers the following aspects:

1. Data download and integration of biodiversity data
2. Set up and application of new R functions
3. Example lake analysis of the outputs

a) Implemented Solution

The tools used for processing the global lake catchment database, as well as the hydrographr R package include the open-source geo-computational software GRASS GIS⁹, GDAL¹⁰, pktools¹¹, AWK¹² and the MSPA tool deployed in command-line bash scripts within the Linux environment (and which can be used in the Windows operating system as well). Due to the computational heavy demands, the tools enable efficient and scalable workflows which we implemented on the high-performance computer cluster (HPC) of Yale University to compute the global lake catchment database. The central working procedure to create the global lake database included the following main processing steps:

1. Buffer creation
2. Intersection lake shapefile and river network
3. Identification of lake outlet
4. Lake catchment delineation

First, we needed to match the different spatial extents of the Hydrography90m and HydroLAKES datasets by applying a buffer around the lakes. This is necessary to reduce the amount of intersection

points from the detailed stream network with the coarser lake polygons. The buffer size is scaled to the size of the lake into four size categories (Table 2).

Table 2 Applied buffer size per lake area to reduce the artefacts between the DEM-derived stream network and the lake polygons. These buffers have been tested on a variety of lake polygons.

Buffer (in meter)	Lake area (in km ²)
100	0.1 - 1
200	1 - 10
300	10 - 100
400	< 100

In the next step we identify all intersection points of the buffered lake polygon and stream network. Here we use the MSPA tool from GuidosToolbox (GWB) to extract the edge of the lake polygon, i.e. the outer boundary. Each intersection point is given an ID and its coordinates, the Hydrography90m stream segment ID, the flow accumulation value of the intersection, as well as the maximum and mean flow accumulation value of the surrounding 3 by 3 pixels which are all saved in an intersection table as a .txt-file. We use this intersection table to identify the intersection point with the highest mean flow accumulation value. This point represents the lake outlet for which we delineate the lake catchment area.

All R functions are based on the above described workflow and tools. However, the R functions access the geo-computational tools in Linux and run the bash scripts in the background. Therefore, the user can simply use the R functions like any other R function without the knowledge of the specific syntax of these third-party tools. Moreover, the R functions provide users additional options to adapt the workflow to their needs. For instance, the R functions let the user choose their input data, buffer sizes and intersection points from which to delineate the lake catchment.

b) Data and Software availability

The hydrographr R package with all its functions, including the new lake functions *extract_lake_ids()*, *get_lake_intersection()* and *get_lake_catchment()* as well as the code is accessible under: <https://github.com/glowabio/hydrographr> and licensed under GNU General Public License v3.0.

Here users can also provide feedback and raise possible issues they have using the functions. The vignette is available under:

https://glowabio.github.io/hydrographr/articles/case_study_lakes.html.

GeoFRESH is licensed under the GNU General Public License v3.0.

c) Innovation and FAIRness

Through the integration of HydroLAKES into the Hydrography90m river network we created a readily accessible, scalable, open-source freshwater data platform, bringing together geospatial lake and river research. We provide users with a coordinated and scalable tool kit which enables them to access and

integrate the available global scale, high resolution hydrological and lake data sets, also accessible to potential users who do not have the in-depth knowledge of GIS-programming or the computational resources. GeoFRESH offers an easy-to-use and intuitive starting point in exploring users' point data in the newly created river and lake continuum. It is also a powerful tool to retrieve valuable preprocessed (e.g. the global lake catchment data) hydrological and lake information as well as a large suit of environmental data without the need to calculate the data for themselves. However, it is possible to recreate the data with the tools and tutorials provided in the hydrographr R package. Here again different user proficiencies are targeted where users can implement the functions in their reproduceable scripts without requiring knowledge of command-line bash scripting and the application of the different geo-processing tools. This integrates our workflows into the R environment commonly used by the scientific community. Advanced users in bash scripting can access the underlying code on our Github webpage (<https://github.com/glowabio/hydrographr>). The interoperability of the R functions is increased through the functioning in both the linux and windows operating systems.

III. Challenges and Gaps

The main challenges of our pilot arose from the computationally heavy demands during the processing of the global lake catchment database while still maintaining an efficient workflow regarding time and computational resources. This made it necessary to iteratively update and monitor the calculations carried out on the HPC. However, this time-consuming process enabled us to now quickly adapt our workflow for upcoming new lake data products. It also shows the necessity of having access to sufficient HPC resources and the expansion and linkage of such vital infrastructure within and for the NFDI4Earth community.

IV. Relevance for the community and NFDI4Earth

Integrating lake data into the Hydrography90m network moves us closer towards a seamless geospatial representation of freshwater habitats. It opens the door for limnologists focusing on lake and river research around the world to use our compiled and fully available data. Our tools target the beginner level as well as the more experienced users in coding through the intuitive point-and-click nature of GeoFRESH for the less experienced users, and adaptable R functions for the more experienced users. Moreover, users with limited computational power or storage limits can benefit greatly from the global lake database which is already preprocessed and accessible through GeoFRESH.

The data, tools and workflow benefit an interdisciplinary field as it connects Earth system (NFDI4Earth) and biodiversity (NFDI4Biodiversity) sciences in the realm of freshwater research. In addition, scientists from other sub-disciplines who are interested in working with geospatial data can easily customize our open-source code and functions towards their needs. For instance, instead of lake polygons, a polygon of a city can be equally used as an input for the `get_lake_intersection()` function, calculating the

intersection points of the city boundary (edge) with e.g. a road network, providing benefits and functionalities to urban planners.

The hydrographr package and GeoFRESH platform are already used in multiple large scale research projects such as AqualNFRA (<https://aquainfra.eu/>), SOS-Water (<https://sos-water.eu/>) and are openly promoted within our research network, on conferences and our websites (<https://glowabio.org/>; <https://glowabio.github.io/hydrographr/>; <https://github.com/glowabio/hydrographr>; <https://geofresh.org/>).

V. Future Directions

This pilot project builds on the previous GeoFRESH pilot^{13,14}, which together provide the basis for the third pilot project starting in 2025. This new pilot will focus on the future directions and emphasize the interoperability of the tools and open science platforms. It will create an easy entry-point for newcomer users and increase the easiness of use and their user experience with GeoFRESH and the hydrographr R package.

The average lake product of the Surface Water and Ocean Topography (SWOT) satellite mission is announced to be available by early 2025 by NASA. This openly available data set will provide a global inventory of lakes and reservoirs with a resolution of 250m by 250m. This high resolution is closer to the 90m resolution of the Hydrography90m stream network which will increase its spatial compatibility and integrate a higher number of lakes into the network. Since we build our data processing workflow also on test data of SWOT, our functions are ready to be used on the upcoming SWOT data. Future plans also include the continuous data curation of the global datasets in line with the ongoing development and user support of the hydrographr R-Package and GeoFRESH platform. Moreover, the long-term vision consists in integrating the cloud optimized into the larger activities of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) as well as to other NFDI initiatives.

VI. References

- 1 Amatulli, G., Marquez, J. G., Sethi, T., Kiesel, J., Grigoropoulou, A., Ublacker, M. M., Shen, L. Q., & Domisch, S. (2022) Hydrography90m: a new high-resolution global hydrographic dataset. *Earth System Science Data* 14, 4525-4550.
- 2 Messenger, M. L., Lehner, B., Grill, G., Nedeva, I., & Schmitt, O. (2016) Estimating the volume and age of water stored in global lakes using a geo-statistical approach. *Nature communications*, 7 (1), 13603.
- 3 Surface Water Ocean Topography (SWOT). (2024) SWOT Level 2 Lake Single-Pass Vector Data Product, Version C. Ver. C. PO.DAAC, CA, USA, <https://doi.org/10.5067/SWOT-LAKESP-2.0> (last access: 19 November 2024).
- 4 Schürz, M., Grigoropoulou, A., García Márquez, J., Torres-Cambas, Y., Tomiczek, T., Flourey, M., Bremerich, V., Schürz, C., Amatulli, G., & Grossart, H. P. (2023) hydrographr: An R package for scalable hydrographic data processing. *Methods in Ecology and Evolution*, 14(12), 2953-2963.

- 5 LIB. Leibniz Institute for the Analysis of Biodiversity Change (LIB). Harmonised freshwaterfish occurrence and abundance data for 12 federal states in Germany. Occurrence dataset <https://doi.org/10.15468/c75fky> accessed via GBIF.org on 2024-09-26.
- 6 The PostgreSQL Global Development Group: PostgreSQL Relational Database System, Version 15.2, <https://www.postgresql.org/> (last access: 06 December 2024).
- 7 PostGIS Development Team: PostGIS spatial extension for the PostgreSQL relational database, Version 3.3.2, <https://postgis.net/> (last access: 06 December 2024).
- 8 Vogt, P., & Riitters, K. (2017) GuidosToolbox: universal digital image object analysis. *European Journal of Remote Sensing*, 50(1), 352-361.
- 9 Neteler, M., Bowman, M. H., Landa, M. & Metz, M. (2012) GRASS GIS: A multi-purpose open source GIS. *Environmental Modelling and Software* 31, 124-130.
- 10 GDAL Development Team: GDAL – Geospatial Data Abstraction Library, Version 3.4.3, Open Source Geospatial Foundation, <http://www.gdal.org> (last access: 06 December 2024).
- 11 McInerney, D., Kempeneers, P., McInerney, D., & Kempeneers, P. (2015) Pktools. Open Source Geospatial Tools: *Applications in Earth Observation*, 173-197.
- 12 Aho, A. V., Kernighan, B. W., & Weinberger, P. J. (2023) The AWK programming language. Addison-Wesley Professional.
- 13 Domisch, S., Bremerich, V., Torres-Cambas Y., Grigoropoulou, A., Marquez, J. G., Amatulli G., Meester, L., Grossart, H. P., Gessner, M., Mehner, T., Adrian, R., (2023) Getting freshwater spatiotemporal data on track – towards the interoperability of freshwater-specific data. NFDI4Earth Pilot Roadmap, Zenodo, 10.5281/zenodo.7888389
- 14 Domisch, S., Bremerich, V., Buurman, M., Kaminke, B., Tomiczek, T., Torres-Cambas, Y., Grigoropoulou, A., Garcia Marquez, J. R., Amatulli, G., Grossart, H.-P., Gessner, M. O., Mehner, T., Adrian, R., & De Meester, L. (2024) GeoFRESH – an online platform for freshwater geospatial data processing. *International Journal of Digital Earth*, 17(1). doi:10.1080/17538947.2024.2391033